

How to Create a Quality DOI for NASA Research Artifacts

NASA researchers are faced with multiple demands for the research artifacts produced with NASA funding. In addition to these, there are also best practices to address to incorporate Open Science components. Researchers also want their work to be impactful, cited by others, and ideally funded for continued work. The metadata needed to satisfy these demands can be bewildering to navigate on one's own.

This how-to guide provides instructions on how to create a DOI with quality metadata for research artifacts submitted to a generalist repository, particularly Zenodo. NASA-funded mission datasets and permanently restricted artifacts should be submitted to the relevant NASA SMD repository. Also, Zenodo can only incorporate submission sizes up to 200 GB per user. If your submission size is larger than that limit, please consider ways to reduce the size while maintaining its scientific purpose. Please contact the relevant NASA SMD repository if such a reduction is not possible (e.g., the Space Physics Data Facility ([SPDF](#)) or the Solar Data Analysis Center ([SDAC](#)) for space and solar physics).

The guide incorporates metadata required by NASA, metadata often used by funders to assess impact, and metadata used by other researchers to discover and validate the artifact (e.g., Madhura et al. 2026¹). Many NASA researchers use Zenodo as the generalist repository of choice, so the steps below are customized to that website. Principal Investigators of NASA-funded work are required to obtain an ORCID, so this how-to begins with that step.

Step 1: Create an ORCID

An ORCID is a unique identifier for researchers. Creating an ORCID for yourself enables others to give you the proper recognition in citations, particularly when another author shares your name or first initial and last name. Having an ORCID also simplifies tracking what publications, presentations, posters, software, data, (and so on) you are listed as an author on. Obtaining this type of identifier is increasingly becoming a requirement for US-funded research. Visit <https://orcid.org/> to easily create one for free.

Step 2: Create a Zenodo Account

Creating a Zenodo account is a simple way to obtain a DOI for a large variety of objects for free. There are other popular options, such as Dryad, FigShare, and DataVerse that offer similar services. For the sake of simplicity, this tutorial shows instructions for how to create a Zenodo account.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19695956>

- Navigate to <https://zenodo.org/> and click the Sign Up button at the top right of the page.
- Click the “Sign up with ORCID” button. If you logged out of your ORCID account, you will need to log in with the email address and password you entered in Step 1. Otherwise, the log-in process should occur automatically.

If you already have a Zenodo account, you can link your new ORCID by logging into Zenodo with your linked GitHub account. Once you are logged in, click on the drop down menu at the top right of the screen, click “Linked accounts”, and add your ORCID there.

Step 3: Select and Prepare the Submission Files

Selecting the Files

In the submission process, you will need to select the type of resource for your submission (e.g., Presentation, Software, or Dataset). So, it is useful to separate the files associated with each into different submissions. Common items included in each type of submission are outlined below.

- **Presentation/Posters:** Usually, the only file you need here is the presentation or poster file itself.
- **Datasets:** The files containing the data are critical to include. Some basic documentation on what data the files contain and how to use the data properly, such as what software you recommend be used to analyze the data, is extremely useful to others to include in the submission. The more complex your data or analysis process is, the more detailed the documentation will need to be for someone else to understand it.
- **Software:** The files containing the code are critical to include. Some basic documentation is extremely useful to include in the submission. It should describe what the software does, how to run it, and what dependencies the software has, including version numbers of those packages, and what language the software is written in with the version number (e.g. Python 3.10). The more complex the software is, the more documentation will be needed by someone else to understand it.

PRO TIP: Computational models are considered by NASA to be software, not models. As a rule of thumb, choose the “Software” resource type if the work is mostly written in a programming language.

Preparing a Preview File

The Zenodo interface provides previews of PDF files, but not for many other common file types. The preview file should be the best starting point for someone to begin exploring your resource. If you have a file type that is simple to convert to PDF form (e.g., text, slides) and would provide a nice preview of or introduction to your materials, convert that file to PDF form. For simpler

cases, that information can be provided in the description field, but there is a 5000 character limit (including HTML formatting) on what will be used for discovery² (see the next section).

- **Presentations/Posters:** The file containing the presentation slides or poster is often converted to PDF and used as the preview.
- **Datasets:** The preview file is often the documentation or analysis instructions.
- **Software:** It is not common for software to have a preview file. If you would like to have one, you could convert the documentation or usage instructions into a PDF and use that file as the preview file.

Once you have the files ready, it is helpful to separate files intended for separate submissions into different folders (see Figure 1 for an example).

Figure 1: Example folder organization, with files for separate submissions grouped into distinct folders.

PRO TIP: Zenodo's size limit for free submissions is 50 GB and 100 files. If your submission is greater than that limit (e.g., a larger dataset), you can use the "[Manage Storage](#)" feature to increase that limit up to 200 GB.

Step 4: Find the needed information

Creating the Zenodo submission in the next step will be much easier if you already have all the needed information collected.

Authors and Contributors

Often, the most tedious but most valuable information to collect is the author and contributor information. The Zenodo interface is constructed so that you can search for authors by name and their ORCID, affiliation, and affiliation identifier (e.g., its [ROR](#)) are automatically incorporated. However, this doesn't always work, even when the person has an ORCID, and it is not always obvious which 'Rachel Brown' is your colleague. Collecting the ORCID from each of your authors directly is a more sure way to correctly indicate them in your submission. You will also need to determine, ideally through discussion, the author order for the submission, who should be placed in the contributor list instead of the author list, and what role to indicate for those in the contributor list. If an author or creator does not have an ORCID and cannot create one, make sure to at least add their family and given names.

² <https://developers.google.com/search/docs/appearance/structured-data/dataset#dataset>

- **Authors/Creators** (ordered list): Name, ORCID
- **Contributors** (ordered list): Name, ORCID, Contributor Role

Affiliations and affiliation RORs are not required by NASA, so there is no need to enter that information manually. If the person has indicated their affiliation in their ORCID profile and have made that information public, then the affiliation and the affiliation ROR should automatically populate in the Zenodo interface. However, you should confirm that the information added by the Zenodo interface for these fields is correct.

PRO TIP: There is a delay between when the person creates or updates information associated with their ORCID and when Zenodo can see that new or updated information. So, encourage your co-authors and contributors to create or update their ORCID profiles **at least one day before** you begin the submission process.

PRO TIP: The ORCID look-up feature on Zenodo will only work for people who have set their ORCID visibility to “Everyone”.

Funding Information

Look through your funding paperwork to locate the information needed for the funding section. The funder name, award title, and award identifier should be indicated in that paperwork. If the funder’s identifier is not indicated in that paperwork, you can use ror.org to search for the funder name and retrieve the funder ROR.

- **Funding:** Funder name, Funder Identifier (e.g., ROR), Award Title, Award Identifier

Example:

- Funder Name: NASA Science Mission Directorate Heliophysics Division
- Funder Identifier: <https://ror.org/03myraf72>
- Award Title: Developing Heliophysics Standards and Cross-science Collaborations
- Award Identifier: NNH24ZDA002N

General Information

The remaining fields are generally simple to create and select in the submission interface. However, you can prepare these beforehand if you prefer.

- Title
- Resource Type (e.g., Presentation, Dataset, or Software)
- Description (at least 50 characters but no more than 5000 characters)
- Version (if a custom version is desired)
- License name
- Reference Publication DOI

The description field should briefly describe what your resource is, what it is expected to be useful for, and other information **important for reuse**. The first 5000 characters will also be used for discovery, so make sure to include the text that would help others discover your work towards the beginning. This text is sometimes copied from documentation.

Zenodo's default license is currently [CC-BY 4.0](#) for all submitted works, which generally works well for posters and presentations. NASA recommends [CC0-1.0](#) for research data, the same license required for mission data. Commonly used licenses for open software are [MIT](#), [BSD-3-Clause](#), or [Apache-2.0](#).

A reference publication is generally a peer-reviewed publication describing the resource and is a common practice for software and data. If there is such a publication for the resource you are submitting, you will need just the publication's DOI.

Citing other works used to create the current submission gives credit to the authors of those artifacts, particularly when those artifacts are datasets or software. Citing these artifacts is a standard research practice, which also helps others understand and trust how your research artifact was created. However, it can be challenging to determine what artifacts should be cited. Several example scenarios are available in [How-To: Citing Critical Artifacts](#).

Step 5: Work through the Zenodo submission process

Figure 2: Navigating through the Zenodo menus to the “New upload” page. The location of the menu depends on the size of your browser window. The “New upload” option is either indicated with three bars (bottom right, bars not shown) or with a plus sign (top right).

Log in to Zenodo using your ORCID (Figure 2, left), then navigate to the “New Upload” page, located in the drop-down menu at the top right of the page, either indicated with three bars (Figure 2, bottom right) or with a plus sign (Figure 2, top right).

Files

Add your prepared files to the submission using either the “Drag and drop” area or the blue “Upload files” button. Select the “Default preview” button for the preview file you prepared.

Basic Information

In the “*Digital Object Identifier*” question, select “No, I need one” to obtain a DOI for the submission. If needed, click on the *Get a DOI now!* button to immediately obtain a DOI for the draft submission. Fill in each field with the prepared information (*Resource type, Title, Publication date, Description, and License*).

PRO TIP: The publication date is usually the date of submission, but in some cases, this is changed to an earlier date (e.g., the presentation date of the uploaded presentation).

Authors are called ‘*Authors/Creators*’ on the Zenodo interface, which has a separate interactive interface. Click on the ‘Add creator’ button following the ‘*Publication date*’ field to add creators. Even if you have the person’s ORCID or the organization’s ROR, it is still better to search for the person or organization by name so that the correct name, identifiers, and affiliation autopopulate instead of entering that information by hand. Select the appropriate author type (Person or Organization), use the search bar to search by the person or organization’s name, and select the name with the correct associated identifier. You may have to scroll in some cases as in the example below (Figure 3). If you are unsure of your selection, you can click the ORCID link to confirm the creator’s identity. Once you are sure of the correct choice, click the name in the drop down list.

The screenshot shows the 'Add creator' dialog box in Zenodo. At the top, there are two radio buttons: 'Person' (selected) and 'Organization'. Below this is a search input field containing the text 'Brian Thomas'. A dropdown menu is open, displaying search results. The first result is 'Thomas, Brian (ORCID: 0000-0003-1623-9035) National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA)'. The second result is 'Thomas, Brian (ORCID: 0000-0002-0090-905X)'. The interface is clean and modern, with a light gray background and blue accents.

Figure 3: Searching for an author through the Zenodo interface. Searching by name, identifier, or affiliation returns a dropdown list of matching records, allowing the correct name, identifier, and affiliation to autopopulate. When multiple people share a name, scroll through the results and use the linked ORCID to verify identity before clicking to select.

The ORCID (person option) or ROR (organization option) identifier of the creator will autopopulate in the *Identifiers* field in the correct format. If the person's ORCID profile is public, then the person's *Affiliation* will also autopopulate. Affiliation identifiers, such as RORs, cannot be entered into Zenodo at this time. Click the blue "Save and add another" button to add more creators, or click the blue "Save" button to save and close the creator interface.

Creators with correctly entered identifiers will have the ORCID symbol next to their names such as pictured below (Figure 4). This feature is currently not supported for organizational authors. You may have to save the record draft before the symbol appears.

Figure 4: Correctly entered author records display the ORCID icon next to the name, confirming the identifier is properly linked.

Recommended Information

Contributors, if any, can be added in this section. The interface is nearly identical to the one for *Authors/Creators*, but additionally requires a role. Choose the most relevant role from the list provided. *Keywords and subjects* can be added in the indicated field. Multiple entries can be added by hitting the 'Enter' key (Windows) or 'Return' key (Mac OS) following each term. You can easily enter the language by searching for and selecting the language in which the submission files are written. If the submission is a software or dataset, also add the *Version*. Otherwise, Zenodo will assume the artifact is the first version (equal to 1.0).

Funding

The default options available under Awards/Grants do not support many NASA-funded works. Click 'Add custom' in this section to properly add the prepared information. Use the *Funder* search bar to find the correct funder. If your work is funded by a particular division, make sure to select that division and not the general NASA option. Compare the prepared funder identifier with that shown in the dropdown list of the funder field once you have entered the funder name to ensure the correct funder is selected (Figure 5). You can copy the identifier into the search bar on [ROR.org](https://ror.org) if additional confirmation is needed.

Enter the award identifier in the *Number* field and the award title into the *Title* field. If the award or grant has an associated URL, such as for the accepted proposal's abstract, it can be entered in the *URL* field. Click the blue Add button to complete the funding entry.

Funder*

- National Aeronautics and Space Administration, United States, 027ka1x80
- National Stroke Association of Malaysia, Malaysia, 00pqehw64
- National Association of State Departments of Agriculture, United States, 02arcr276

Figure 5: Organizations with RORs matching the shown search term. Searching by organization name or identifier returns a dropdown list of matching records, allowing the correct name and identifier to autopopulate. When multiple organizations share a name, scroll through the results and use the linked ROR to verify identity before clicking to select.

Alternate Identifiers

This section is typically not needed for submissions, but can be used to include existing identifiers for the item, such as ARKs or handles. Software Heritage hash identifiers (SWHIDs) for software are often automatically retrieved if the software is indexed through that service. For more information, see <https://www.softwareheritage.org/software-hash-identifier-swhid/>.

Related Works

This is the section where the reference publication's DOI should be entered. To enter the reference publication DOI, select the "Cite With" option in the *Relation* dropdown menu. If that option is not available, the 'Is described by' option will suffice. Enter the full DOI link of the reference publication into the *Identifier* field (e.g., <https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ab4f7a>). In the *Scheme* drop down list, select "DOI". In the *Resource type* drop down list, select "Publication / Journal Article".

If citations to additional artifacts are desired, then further instructions are available in the *How Do I Cite Them?* section of [How-To: Citing Critical Artifacts](#), including the recommended *Relation* options for various scenarios. To add additional related works, begin by clicking the *Add related work* button.

References

If an identifier is not available for a particular item to be cited, the full citation to the item can be copied into the *Reference string* field (example below). To add additional reference strings, click the 'Add reference' button.

The SunPy Community et al. 2020 ApJ 890 68

Software

This section is only relevant for software. The most important field in this section is the *Repository URL*. If the software is hosted publicly on GitHub, GitLab, CodeOcean, or similar websites, put the link to the software in this field, e.g., <https://github.com/sunpy/sunpy>. If the code is not publicly available, the link to the website where access can be requested should be entered here, e.g., <https://amgeo.colorado.edu/>.

Programming language is also supported in this section, but be warned that versions of those programming languages are not, such as Python 2.x compared to Python 3.x. The options listed for *Development Status* are defined at <https://www.repostatus.org/>.

Remaining sections

If the artifact is a Thesis or as part of a journal, book, report, or proceedings, the related information can be added in the *Publishing information* section. If the artifact was presented at a conference, such as a presentation or a poster, the information for the conference can be added in the *Conference* section. If any domain specific fields are needed, that information belongs in the *Domain specific fields* section.

Visibility

NASA policy specifically calls for the removal or reduction of embargos on NASA-funded research artifacts, including data and software (see [NASA's SPD-41a](#) section III). In the scenario where the research artifact cannot be publicly released at the time of submission, the *Restricted* option in this section can be selected. This is commonly encountered for research artifacts supporting a peer-reviewed publication that is not yet accepted or a research artifact not yet approved for public release. In most cases, the restriction is temporary, so the *Apply an embargo* checkbox should be selected, the release date entered in the *Embargo until* field, and a brief reason entered in the *Embargo reason* field. If NASA determines the research artifact must remain restricted, do not check the *Apply an embargo* box. Note that submitters can share restricted submissions with others through Zenodo's sharing options, which are available before (blue *Share* button) and after (see *Record Management* section below) publication on Zenodo. If the artifact is cited in an article, make sure to change the visibility to *Public* when the article is accepted for publication if there are no justified permanent restrictions.

Publish

Once all the desired fields are completed, click the *Save draft* and *Preview* buttons to ensure the information entered is accurate. After review, click the *Publish* button to publish the submission. Note that publication of the submission is permanent and cannot be retracted, but changes are possible through the [edit interface](#) in the first 30 days.

Record Management

If edits to a submission are required after submission, then those edits can be performed through the *Manage record* button on the artifacts landing page. If the changes are only to the information entered and not to the uploaded files, then the *Edit* button is the correct choice. If the edits include changes to the files, then a new version is needed. Various sharing options are available through the *Sharing* button, including sharing with specific people (e.g., peer reviewers of a journal article) or generating links with varying permissions that expire. Specific additional options are available for restricted or embargoed submissions.